

PADDY PESTS INFORMATION SYSTEM

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Abstract. The system is a computerized system for 'Farmers'. Myanmar is an agricultural country, and it has always traditionally been Myanmar's main industry, employing over half of the labor force. The agriculture sector is one of the most important sectors of the country's economy, and agricultural goods are Burma's second-largest export commodity. The sector normally contributes nearly one-third of the country's GDP and employs more than half of the workforce. The Website for Farmland Rights is a system that collects information related to farmland rights. Overall, this project is mainly intended for farmers who grow rice to increase the yield of rice. The system is implemented with PHP platform and MySQL database.

Keyword: pests, analysis, system, farmers

INTRODUCTION

Agriculture is the practice of cultivating plants and livestock in order to provide facilities the human beings. In the rise of the sedentary human lifestyle agriculture was the key development. The cultivation of plant and food grains began years ago in order to provide food to the city population. Agriculture is the main need for the people to live in the society. Agriculture is the main source of livelihood, and also it provides a source for the people to earn. Most of the population in the rural areas is dependent on agriculture as their main source of income. This system is mainly intended for farmers who grow rice to increase the yield of rice. One of the main objectives of a system is that it is easy to identify rice insects (pests) and has a lot of agricultural knowledge. So, I want to design a paddy pests analysis system that can help farmers by giving them a lot of knowledge about agriculture.

PROBLEM

The most important agricultural commodity of Myanmar is Rice. There are two important things for the growth of rice. The first one is Farmland which is essential for growing rice. The second is farmers who are persons who promoted the growth of plants, land, or crops through labor and attention. There are two types of farmers: those who own the farmland and those who work on the farmland. Farmers can get many privileges if they own farmland rights.

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Nowadays, farmers have to go to the relevant offices and apply for authorization with documents. In the age of technological progress, this system was created to be able to apply for authorization with devices instead of applying with papers.

APPROACH

The system consists of two main sides: admin side and user side. Admin is required to login. Only after login, admins can manage all the data in the system. And admins can add new admins and remove admins. Users can easily learn a lot of agricultural knowledge and pests that damage rice and yield on this website. This system is developed in Myanmar language therefore users (farmers) can easily understand and use it.

The admin must login first. After logging in, admin can manage the details of system data. Also, admin can add new admins and delete admins. Moreover, the admin will be able to view the list of the users (farmers). the system flow diagram for users (farmers) is presented. The users (farmers) can view the detail of agricultural knowledge. They are paddy seeds, pesticide laws, agricultural books and paddy plant diseases and etc. The users (farmers) must login first. After logging in, users can make analysis paddy pests and plant disease analysis then read the detail about of paddy pests and plant diseases and detection ways.

Figure 1: System Flow Diagram

Figure 2: Database Design

An Entity Relationship Diagram uses data modeling techniques that can help define business processes and serve as the foundation for a relational database. An ERD attribute can be denoted as a primary key, which identifies a unique attribute, or a foreign key, which can be assigned to multiple attributes. A cardinality notation can then define the attributes of the relationship between the entities. In the database, there are six data tables for administrator and five data tables for the user. The tables are users, feedback, news, announcement, appointment and medicine. The figure 2 shows database design for all the data tables and their relationship of the database.

RESULTS

An agricultural knowledge website for farmers is a website that can be watch easily about the agricultural details. This system can search paddy’s pests and diseases with paddy’s plant’s damage shape and paddy’s plant sizes. With this analysis, farmers were needed to have only one account. The account can be opened with a phone number. Therefore, People who works in agriculture are mostly farmers, so it’s not a problem that they don’t understand email with just having the internet on your mobile phone or other devices without logging in. After logging in, users can make analysis paddy pests and plant disease analysis then read the detail about of paddy pests and plant diseases and detection ways. This system provides the

services for users to apply for agricultural knowledge but not all. In this system, users can only apply for agricultural pharmacy for townships in Hinthada District. If farmers study pests and diseases, they will only check for pests and diseases affecting paddy.

Figure 3: Implementation of this system

CONCLUSION

Myanmar is an agricultural country, and it has always traditionally been Myanmar's main industry, employing over half of the labor force. The agriculture sector is one of the most important sectors of the country's economy, and agricultural goods are Burma's second-largest export commodity. A total of 12.8 million hectares out of 67.6 million hectares of land in Burma are cultivated. Also, in the government sector, computers are being used especially in calculating statistics. The principal crop of Ayeyarwady Region is rice, and the division is called the "granary of Burma." Therefore, the system can help the farmers to increase the yield of rice. Pesticide laws are also available for people opening an agro-pharmacy. And then, as farmers, they can know how to properly use pesticides. I can tell my parents a lot of agricultural knowledge accurately.

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